

**THE CHALLENGES OF LEADERSHIP TO GOOD GOVERNANCE
IN NIGERIA UNDER A DEMOCRATIC REGIME.**

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Abstract

Leadership is a very important variable in the nature, state and character of any nation. Leadership and the form of leadership that they provide shape the way in which state policies are made and the impact on the generality of the people. State on its own cannot make policies; it depends on the political elite to do this. Thus, it is the political elites or the decision makers of a state who determine the purpose and course of actions at both the domestic and international levels. Ironically, the conditions of Nigeria and Nigerians over the years have remained pathetic. This has been attributed to a number of factors among which is leadership failure. The leadership has been described as not focused, sincere, honest and corrupt. All these vices, it is said lead to bad government. The resultant effect is the general level of poverty, insecurity, unemployment and deprivation. The paper finally submits that to redress the situation, there is the urgent need to reform the country through honest, transparent, dedicated, committed e.g, detribalized, national leader who could transform the country to a truly federal state with every citizen feeling a genuine sense of belonging^m every part of the country.

Introduction

The leadership question has become a recurring issue in the discourse on the Nigeria project. The political elite or decision makers (Leaders) have been object of vilification, condemnation and disdain in view pervasive and persistent political crisis. Nigerian leaders have been accused of being responsible for the present state of Nigeria which Seteoulu (2004) aptly described as been characterized by:

Huge external debt overhang, net capital flight, disinvestment collapse of social infrastructures, food crisis and insecurity, over devalued national currency, pervasive poverty, homelessness and under development, unpopular, repressive and alienating economic policies.

The descriptions above negate the estimation of most observers of Nigeria state who see the country has having the potential to be dynamic economy. This optimism is premised on the available and abundant human and material resources which the country is endowed with by nature.

It is of course true that the economic fortunes of a country are determined by a variety of factors. In the case of Nigeria, the collapse of the international oil market in the 1980s is obviously one of the major causes. It led to a drastic fall in national earnings, concomitantly in the capacity to import needed consumer goods and industrial raw materials and spare parts. Besides, the structural adjustment programmed (SAP) which was adopted by the Babangida administration in 1986 as panacea, has proven in-capable of solving the economic and political problems of the country. The removal of subsidy, trade liberalization, currency devaluation, privatization and other policy instruments of SAP yielded only few benefits. "Their overall impact was to worsen inflation, unemployment infrastructure decay, poverty, ethic militia, insecurity etc. however, in the view of Enamor (1997).

The most critical variable in the explanation of acute economic, social and political crisis in which Nigeria is currently mired is failure of leadership).

One will but agree with the above submission because, as earlier pointed out, it is the political elites or decision makers (Leaders) who determine the nature and structure of a state, therefore the idiosyncrasies of leaders go a long way to

determining policies that are formulated and implemented.

There is no doubt that Nigeria is highly endowed with natural and human resources. The country has oil and Gas, numerous mineral resources like coal, bauxite, iron and steel columbite etc. in abundance. Similarly, with a population about one hundred and seventy million men and women (NPC: 2011) who are highly productive there can be divorce from poor handling or harnessing these resources in appropriate qualities order than leadership.

The failure of Nigerian state is therefore blamed mostly oil leadership failure. The focus of this paper therefore is to examine the problem of leadership in Nigeria over the years. Some manifestation of these failures would be examined.

Effort will be made to recommend some solutions to these problems, so that, if applied; the problems can be resolved and Nigeria can arrive at the Eldorado envisaged by her founding fathers.

Conceptual Clarification

Theories of leadership assume that there are shared goals and objectives and that a leader established the goals, purpose and objectives of the collective will. In addition, the leader creates structures through which the goals and objectives can be achieved (Pogonson 1994). The truth is that it is only a strong and effective leadership that can provide purposeful goals and objectives and Vice Versa. With good focused and purposeful leadership, a country is likely to be a place for all to live. Thus, among all factors that determine the condition of a country, leadership occupies a vital position. Leadership has several definitions. Just like other concepts in the social science family. According to Penguin dictionary of politics;

Leadership is a quality which in theory signifies the ability of a person or a group of persons that persuade others to act by inspiring them and making them believe that action proposed course of action is the correct one.

According to James Stoner cited in Mimi & (1997) leadership is viewed as "a behavior which induces energetic, emotionally, committed cooperative followers and influencing the task related activities of group member".

From the two samples of various definitions of leadership given above, it can be noted that leadership is not specific abilities. In recent times the quality of

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leadership is said to reside not only in an individual, but in role that is played within specified social system. Also in contemporary times, leadership is seen as group function or characteristics instead of individual action.

For the purpose of this work we conceive leadership as that group of individuals who plan, co-ordinates directs and control the activities of those individuals for whom they have the responsibility, so as to accomplish the goals/objectives of other groups. And since we are concerned with a country (Nigeria) in this paper, leadership here means the group of individuals who plan, coordinate, direct and control the activities of Nigerians towards achieving the national interest of the entire country.

Democracy is fundamentally about the exercise of power by the people. It, should principally focus on how the people exercise their power in determining who manages the affairs of their countries and how far they go in exercising direction and control over those representatives in order to ensure the protection and promotion of their rights and enhancement of their, general welfare. Based on the above conception of democracy, good governance would be attained where the principles of democracy are adopted in governing the people. These principles or tenets of democracy require to attain good governance are listed by Motie (2008) to include:

1. Accountability and Transparency
2. Development of infrastructures
3. Employment and Security
4. Popular Participation
5. Development of Political Institutions (Political Parties,)
6. Independent Electoral institutions
7. Free Press and Freedom of Association
8. Independent Judiciary
9. The Rule of Law
10. Civilian control of the Military and its institutions.

The Existence of all itemized principles in a polity points to good governance as a democratically formed government which embeds these tenants in its governance of the state.

The Nigeria State, Leadership and Governance

Nigeria emerge as a nation after about forty years of colonization (1900-1960) during that period; it was the colonial masters that dictated the economic and political activities of the country. The country's socio-economy was under the heavy weight of colonial domination and manipulation. The independence granted the country in 1960 succeeded in breeding local bourgeoisie, who emerged as leaders. These new leaders only ensure the consolidation of the capitalist mode of production and accumulation policy of the colonialists.

The colonial policy bequeathed to Nigeria a parliamentary system of government. This system was based oil the principles of fusion of power among the organs of government. It also entails the principle of collective responsibility bicephalous executive system, strong party discipline and strong opposition parties. The country was administered oil the premise of a regional structure within the context of the federal system allowed the regions to pursue policies and programmes hinged oil their historical specificities.

Besides, the parliamentary system of government evolved leadership that had immense fellowership and legitimacy. Seteolu (2004) posits that these strength were used to mobilize the people behind policies. Each region was under the leadership of visionary, dynamic and charismatic leaders in persons of Chief Obafemi Awolowo (West), Sir Ahmad Bello (North) and Dr. Nnamadi Azikwe (East). Similarly during this period it was observed that political parties were disciplined with clear cut people-oriented manifestoes. However, the political situation of the country due largely to the contradictions inherent in the formations of the country by the colonialist led to the collapse of the first republic in 1966. For example, in the formations of the nation and the component parts, no consideration was given to the people cultural, religious and ethnic differences. The effect of this is the constant, ethnic clashes, mutual suspicion and lack of sense of belonging to the nation state. All these vices are responsible for the seemingly Under developed nature of Nigeria.

Another perspective of the Nigeria state, leadership and governance sees the problem of Nigeria as that emanating from its formation. According to Chief Obafemi Awolowo, one of the foundation fathers of Nigeria, lie posits that.

Nigeria is not a nation. It is a mere geographical expression. There are no Nigeria in the solve sense as there are English or welsh or Freach. The world Nigeria

is merely a distractive appellation to distinguish those who live within the boundaries of Nigeria from those who do not. Awolowo (1947) cited in Abubakar (2004).

Implicitly, Nigeria is a country with multi-ethnic, multi-religious and multi-cultural identities. Though, the nationalists who struggled for the country's independence did it on the platform of one Nigeria; no sooner than the independence was achieved than they began to promote ethnic, religious and sectional interests. According to Usman (2000) cited in Abubakar (op.cit), leaders resorted to mobilizing ethnic identities to capture state power III the early and post-independence epoch. The mobilization of primordial identities in the pursuit of state power Ultimately culminated in the tragic civil war. One, it was a major challenge to the national cohesion of the country. The ethnic coloration of the war gave insight into this conclusion. Secondly, the Successful prosecution of this war by Nigeria and the consequential unity of the country at the end of the war point to the fact that there Call still be unite in diversity. However as Ake (1996), cited in Abubakar (2004) rightly pointed out, the competition and conflict among nationalities, ethnic groups and communities weakened the solidarity of the people.

The post-independence Nigerian leaders were obviously regional leaders, not national, each of the regional leaders used the control of state power to strengthen their material base. As neocolonial leaders who believed in maintaining the status quo, they embarked on nationalization of industries, imposition of coercion in the labour process and political control of regional commodity boards (Abubakar: 2004 157), political power, therefore became synonymous with access to wealth and reproduction of hegemonic faction of political elite. Thus, Nigerian leadership breeding process has remained through the use of state resources to obtain and retain power. The implication of this mode of breeding leader has a number of negative implications on the quality of leaders that have governed and still governing Nigeria. (Abubakar op cit P. 157), list four these consequences thus;

- i. It intensified factional as well as ethno-regional competition for state power.
- ii. Since the control of state power is synonymous with wealth and security, politics became zero-sum game with high possibilities of violence and political instability.

- iii. Monopolization of, state power and apparatus became powerful arsenals for setting political differences thereby deepen the processes of exclusion, marginalization and deprivation.
- iv. The exacerbation of regional disparities in the resource distribution and overall development further reinforced the problem of national question thereby foreclosing the possibilities of any meaningful nation-building Project by the political leadership.

Thus, it cannot be an overstatement to conclude that colonialism and its after effect has terrible repercussion on Nigeria state and its governance. It is greatly responsible for the quality and ability of leaders that have governed and are still governing the country. The military that interchanged leadership of with Nigeria with civilian leaders did not fair better. The dominance of this military in the governance of the country for a large part of the fifty-one years of her independence not only entrenched the culture of authoritarianism and the official use of political violence as an instrument of state policy, but even more fundamentally, militarism ill Nigeria undermined the residual democratic values in the political system, recentralized political power at the federal level to the detriment of the periphery and intensified the challenges to the socio-political and economic development of the country. Literature abound that point to the fact that the military has not only heightened divisive tendencies in Nigeria, it has portrayed the country in bad shape internationally. For example Ihonbere 1997, 1998, 1999, 2000; and Olikoshi and Leadkso, 1996, posit that;

Militarism, especially under the autocratic regimes of Babangida and Abacha, not only deepened the divisions in the country along ethnic, regional and religions lines, but even more fundamentally, they recentralized federal power, marginalized minority ethnic groups, exacerbated violence, abuse of human rights, corruption and the mismanagement of state resources.

Implicitly therefore, both the civilian and military leaders that have ruled the country in its fifty-one years of independence have failed the nation in terms of good governance. Among tile legacies of military rule in Nigeria is that it subverted the residual foundation of Nigeria's federalism through the monopolization of political and economic powers at the center. This centralization of power and resources at the

center not only exacerbated patronage and clientalism/corruption in governance but it also deepened the marginalization of sub-national unity thereby increasing apathy and cynicism towards the national development project. At inception, Nigeria's federalism was meant to form a united country from the various nations that make up the country, through devolution of power from the centre to the federating units, unfortunately, in the view of Agbje (1999) this could not be;

*Largely because of the reversal of its earlier
devolutionary logic for re-centralization occasioned by
poor and short sighted political leadership*

Thus it is an undisputable fact that both the civilian and military leadership have failed Nigeria.

Manifestations of Failure in the Nigerian State

Nigeria has for long been exhibiting features of a failed state. The manifestation of state failure is pervasive and ubiquitous. One of the critical areas of this manifestation is the infrastructural decay. Power, a major input of economic and social development is not only epileptic it is so erratic and unreliable that many industries and other productive ventures that rely on public power supply are made to pay for electricity not consumed. Presently power generation stands at a mere 3,400 megawatts. This is grossly inadequate to service thousands of industries and domestic requirements of the country.

The 3,500 kilometers of rail tracks are largely idle throughout the country. The implication of this is that the road network is subjected to unnecessary stress due to excessive use by long trucks which carry heavy haulage which would have been conveniently and cheaply conveyed by the rail system. This has led to most highways in the country becoming death traps as a result of daily ghastly motor accidents leading to the death of innocent citizens.

The health and education sectors are not left out. Hospitals have become mere consulting clinics without adequate drugs and qualified personnel and equipment. The resultant effect is that the "well to do" among us go for treatment abroad while those who cannot afford overseas trips die innocently due to lack of adequate health care services.

Education from primary to tertiary level is becoming expensive. The federal universities are inadequate to cope with the demand.

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The state governments are also embarking on tertiary level education with some of them charging exorbitant fees. The private Sectors too are establishing universities but charging prohibitive fees. Thus the poor who cannot afford the high fees of state and private universities, also found it difficult to get admitted into the federal universities due to other encumbrances put in the name of quota Systems, catchments etc. at both the lessons under tree and in dilapidated structures while the ratio of teacher to students is still wide. Consequently all these inadequacies have resulted in the controversy as to whether the standard of education in Nigeria is falling or rising.

Agriculture, once the main-stay of the economy and employer of 65% of the workforce has declined to the extent that Nigeria now spends over \$ 3 billion annually on food imports. (World Bank report 2011). Apart from poverty, hunger and food insecurity, which steers everyone in the (ace, the situation has been compounded by high level of insecurity, sectarian crisis and ethnic violence in parts of the country. The level of insecurity in the country has now risen to Harming rate which is presently likening Nigeria to terror state. In its Thursday June 30, 2011 edition, the punch editorial quoted a United State based fund for peace as saying that

Nigeria appears closer to the brink than ever before "it goes further to say that Nigeria retained its 14th position out of 177 countries analyzed, the same spot it hold in 2010, the country was only a head of the world's 13 most miserable place namely, Somalia, Sudan, Chad, Congo (DR) Haiti, Zimbabwe, Afghanistan central African Republic, Iraq, coted'Ivoire, Guinea, Pakistan and Yemen.

In the opinion or observers, the sorry picture painted above is as a result of weak state institutions like leadership, political parties the parliament etc. corruption, sectarianism, economic adversity and contest for political power. Have all combined to place Nigeria In its present state.

The picture painted above is really pathetic but it is the truth. If, as earlier pointed out in this paper, duality of a country's leadership determines its condition, then all the woes can substantially be blamed oil Nigeria leadership. One can also observe that it appears mostly of Nigeria's past and present leaders are ill-prepared for the offices they occupied or that they are out-right not qualified to occupy the

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position. So many of them appeal- not to have the political will, the charisma and the will to rule. However, this is not to say there are not exceptions. At least among the military and civilian leaders of Nigeria, there have been occasions where the duality and personal attributes of some of them have come play significant roles in molding the country. This may have accounted for the continued existence of the country as a single entity and the little progress made.

Way Forward

The picture of Nigeria nation painted above call for concern and concerted effort oil all Nigerians to find, solution to the problems.

The starting point is to look into the origin and composition of the country. Though it is a truism that Nigeria is not a nation, but fifty-one years of co-existence is lone time enough to enable us Understand ourselves, appreciate our differences and harness it to forge unity in our existence should be considered. In this sense, we should go back to true federalism where each ethnic or regional entity should be recognized and treated as all equal and willing member of the federation. Accordingly, the process of this will have to lunched deliberate policy measures aimed at reinventing and rehabilitating the structure of the state as well as key institutions of society with a view to enhancing an effective system of good governance that is sensitive not only to the requirement of economic rationality but above all social welfare of the people. The restructuring of the Nigerian state within the current democratic transition must necessarily transcend the limited clamours for state creation, resources control and related aspect of power devolution. In addition, it should involve factoring in a holistic reinvention of the structures and institutions of governance with a view to deepen the democratic culture of popular participation, accountability and transparency in the exercise of power. This will increase the prospects of consolidating democratic governance. Eventually, this will help to institutionalize the quest for a total national reformation within the framework of a development strategy.

Another way out of the present state of Nigeria nation is to put in place a mechanism that would ensure a national cohesion, communal harmony and stability. This can be done through government factoring into its policies and programmes conscious strategies for strengthen civic institution such as political parties, labour unions association etc, as bulwarks against anti-democratic tendencies. Secondly the

problem of deprivation, poverty, unemployment communal violence and manipulation of ethno-religious identities for security and political reasons be solved holistically.

Presently, political offices are too lucrative in Nigeria. The fat salaries and allowances paid to political office holders make the search for it a do or die affairs. This makes position of leadership too costly for qualified people to aspire to attain. Therefore, the holders of particular certificate in particular professional calling, for example, "The position of the president may be equated with that of a professor in the university and down the line like that. The advantage inherent here is that less qualified individuals could not aspire to occupy the place. And if benefit that would accrue is not as surreptitious as it is presently, it may not attract the present level of agitation it is attracting. The parliament should be made a part time assignment. It should be remunerated also on parts time bases.

Similarly proactive policy that would ensure real unity in diversity should be explored. This is because unity endures where diverse groups feel themselves to be part and parcel of an existing national bargain. They do not feel discriminated against in the existing socio-economic and political order. They would also feel a sense of belonging equity and responsiveness if they are assured of getting what rightly belong to them as member of a country, necessarily because their "own" occupies the highest office in the land. Therefore, the desperation to produce political leader would be reduce to the bearest minimum.

Conclusion

In this paper effort has been made to examine leadership situation and its effect on good governance in Nigeria. We established that a lot of problems are confronting the country but bulk of these problems centre on leadership failure of the state. Some manifestation of the failure of the state were also discussed. In the final analysis, the paper submits that true federalism, committed, transparent, dynamic, honest, trustworthy, detribalized leaders are the necessary antidotes to the challenges of leadership in Nigeria.

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